

DUAL-T Focus group topic guide

Questions
1. Please introduce each other to the group and tell us the story of how you got into literary translation.
2. Imagine I came to you and said 'I have developed a useful technology tool for literary translation'. When you picture it, what kind of things can this tool do?
3. Postediting is the practice of editing a text that has been previously translated by machine translation. How does the skillset of a literary translator differ from that of a literary posteditor?
4. One of the main selling points of postediting for literary translation is that it helps to save time, potentially allowing literary translators to take on more work. What are your thoughts on postediting in relation to the economic dimension of the literary translation profession?
5. How do you picture the literary translation industry in 10 years?
6. Ideally, where would you like the literary translation industry to be in 10 years?
7. If there is one thing you would like literary translators/technology developers to know about your job, what would it be?
8. Of all the things we talked about today, which one would you say is the most important to you?